

Designing custom homes for hollow- dwelling animals

Words by
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The housing crisis – a problem familiar to many architects – affects nonhuman beings too. The shortage of tree hollows is one of many examples.

Globally, thousands of bird and mammal species depend on tree hollows for sheltering from weather, hiding from danger, and raising young. Most of these animals cannot build their own hollows. Instead, they rely on cavities made by woodpeckers, termites, or decay-causing organisms. A tree planted today will not support suitable hollows for decades or even centuries. Urgent action is needed to support hollow-dwelling animals while trees regenerate and mature.¹

Human-made hollows, such as nest boxes, can offer some respite.² But conventional nest boxes encounter issues that parallel the shortcomings of modernist approaches to human housing. Standardisation and mass production make objects cheap and easy to produce but limit opportunities to adjust designs for local conditions. Resulting shapes, materials, and performances of such artificial replacements differ significantly from that of tree hollows. Consequences can be severe when nest boxes overheat,³ break,⁴ or fail to attract target species.⁵

Trained in architecture, I now work with ecologists and designers to overcome the limitations of artificial hollows. Within the interdisciplinary research group, Deep Design Lab, my research pursues habitat-creation projects that respond to local ecologies and cultures. Makers of artificial hollows are increasingly interested in such approaches. For example, recent nest-box designs from the Wildlife Safe Havens project feature artworks by local and Indigenous artists. Other artificial hollows try to look like the arboreal termite-nests in nearby forests. Our research shows exciting opportunities to develop innovative artificial hollows by adopting computational approaches from architectural design.⁶ Until now, these approaches required technical expertise and specialised tools, making them unfeasible within community-led projects.

In response, we are developing the prosthetic hollow configurator: a publicly accessible tool that helps people design custom homes for hollow-dwelling animals. The configurator aims to bridge the gap between two challenges: developing well-performing hollows and encouraging community-based conservation. While online configurators usually aim to sell products such as furniture, Bee Home by Space 10 offers a precedent for how such platforms can serve both humans and other animals. Using opensource technologies, online configurators allow anyone to customise designs to suit their unique circumstances.

Want to install a hollow in your local park or backyard?

Step 1 Design:

Select a target species that lives near you, adjust the shape according to personal preferences, and enter the size of the host-tree for easy installation and stable attachment.

Step 2 Manufacturing:

To build the hollow yourself, enter the dimensions of materials you already have, or select one of the listed materials. The configurator will provide recipes to make organic materials and an augmented-reality template on your smartphone to guide assembly. Alternatively, download the 3D model and connect with a local makerspace to have your hollow built professionally. The configurator lists several digital-fabrication services to help you find an option that suits your time constraints, budget, and other requirements. Each selection you make updates estimates on costs, manufacturing times, lifespans, wastage, and the carbon emissions.

Step 3 Deployment:

Select from installation and monitoring options. These include microclimate sensors, cameras for observing animals inside the hollows, and periodic hollow-inspections by professionals.

This project is an outcome of international collaboration between researchers, industrial partners, land managers, and local councils. We are installing prototypes in the field and testing the platform with communities in south-eastern Australia and northern Italy. Feedback from this testing will inform continual refinement of the configurator's algorithm. At the moment, the configurator provides designs for two species: the powerful owl (*Ninox strenua*) and the boreal owl (*Aegolius funereus*). More sites and species are coming soon.

In the near future, you will be able to upload site-specific data to automate the design of hollows. Using software already available on smartphones, you can 3D scan the host-tree to create a custom-fitted hollow. Machine learning makes it possible to optimise hollows based on 3D scans of habitat structures like tree hollows or termite nests.

This workflow is in active testing. As it stands, the configurator provides a preliminary but practical tool that sets out to benefit more-than-human communities. It supports participatory

design practices and encourages community engagement. For example, its interface is suitable for hollow-building workshops with school children and local friends-of-nature groups. The availability of do-it-yourself and professional options makes the benefits of computationally designed hollows more broadly accessible.

This project is significant as an example that can work for other sites, species, and habitat structures. If you would like to use our techniques or work with nonhuman clients who could benefit, please get in touch. ■

Dan Parker is a designer and researcher in the Faculty of Architecture, Building and Planning at the University of Melbourne. His PhD investigates innovative design approaches that can support coexistence between humans and other animals in urban environments.

Previous page:

Boreal owl (*Aegolius funereus*) looking out from nesting hollow, photo by Gary Schultz, Alamy.

Left:

Design, manufacturing, and installation of a prosthetic hollow using the online configurator. Top: Installation of a prosthetic hollow for the boreal owl (*Aegolius funereus*) in northern Italy. Top-middle: Design of the prosthetic hollow on the configurator's webpage. Bottom-middle: Assembly of the prosthetic hollow using the configurator's augmented-reality guide on smartphone. Bottom: Rendering of the prosthetic hollow with a soil-based material from the configurator's recipe list.

Notes

¹ Manning, Adrian D., Phillip Gibbons, Joern Fischer, Damon Oliver, and David B. Lindenmayer. 2012. "Hollow Futures? Tree Decline, Lag Effects and Hollow-Dependent Species." *Animal Conservation* 16 (4): 395-405. <https://doi.org/10/f47v3m>.

² Goldingay, Ross L., David Rohweder, and Brendan Taylor. 2020. "Nest Box Contentions: Are Nest Boxes Used by the Species They Target?" *Ecological Management & Restoration* 21 (2): 115-22. <https://doi.org/10/dxdq>.

³ Griffiths, Stephen R., Kylie A. Robert, and Christopher S. Jones. 2022. "Chainsaw Hollows Carved into Live Trees Provide Well Insulated Supplementary Shelters for Wildlife During Extreme Heat." *Wildlife Research*. <https://doi.org/10/hzk7>.

⁴ Lindenmayer, David B., Alan Welsh, Christine Donnelly, Mason Crane, Damian Michael, Christopher Macgregor, Lachlan McBurney, Rebecca Montague-Drake, and Philip Gibbons. 2009. "Are Nest Boxes a Viable Alternative Source of Cavities for Hollow-Dependent Animals? Long-Term Monitoring of Nest Box Occupancy, Pest Use and Attrition." *Biological Conservation* 142 (1): 33-42. <https://doi.org/10/fqpr7n>.

⁵ Lindenmayer, David B., Mason Crane, Megan C. Evans, Martine Maron, Philip Gibbons, Sarah Bekessy, and Wade Blanchard. 2017. "The Anatomy of a Failed Offset." *Biological Conservation* 210 (Part A): 286-92. <https://doi.org/10/ggb53b>.

⁶ Parker, Dan., Stanislav Roudavski, Theresá M. Jones, Nick Bradsworth, Bronwyn Isaac, Martin T. Lockett, and Kylie Soanes. 2022. "A Framework for Computer-Aided Design and Manufacturing of Habitat Structures for Cavity-Dependent Animals." *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 13 (4): 826-41. <https://doi.org/10/gpggfj>.